

ODYSSEUS

NEWSLETTER

1 s t I s s u e

ABOUT THE PROJECT

ODYSSEUS European project is expected to improve border crossing experience for travelers and border authorities' staff, while maintaining security and monitoring of movements across land and sea EU external borders. The aim of this project is to support the safety and integrity of the European space, reducing illegal movements of people and goods across those borders, and protecting fundamental rights of biometrical identity travelers

Learn about the project's most significant news and updates!

<https://odysseusproject.eu/>

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Pilot Use Cases

The **ODYSSEUS platform** will be demonstrated through three real-life scenarios, each incorporating clear, realistic, and verifiable short- and long-term goals.

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Kick-off meeting

A promising start

The ODYSSEUS project kick-off meeting was held in Bucharest, Romania, on January 26 and 27, 2023. The primary aim of the meeting was to introduce the core concepts of the project to all consortium members. Partners had a chance to connect and get involved in open discussions centered around the primary objective of the project.

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1st Press Release

The Launch of the ODYSSEUS project

Unobtrusive Technologies for Secure and Seamless
Border Crossing for Travel Facilitation

PRESS RELEASE

21 February 2023

Launch of EU-funded project "ODYSSEUS"

Better protection, faster identity verification at the border
with EU-funded project "ODYSSEUS".

The newly launched ODYSSEUS European project is expected to improve border crossing experience for travelers and border authorities' staff, while maintaining security and monitoring of movements across land and sea EU external borders. The aim of this project is to support the safety and integrity of the European space, reducing illegal movements of people and goods across those borders, and protecting fundamental rights of travelers.

ODYSSEUS also aims to enhance customs and supply chain security through better prevention, detection, deterrence, and fight of illegal activities, involving flows of goods across EU external border crossing points and through the supply chain, minimising disruption to trade flows.

The new project will provide a holistic framework for improving border checks performed by the authorities and facilitate travelling for citizens. A combination of strong multi-behavioral and biometric continuous user identity verification mechanisms will ensure the identification of the citizens, allowing them to cross the border without any interruption or queue. In the meantime, a novel luggage and baggage check will allow citizens' vehicles and cargos to be remotely checked on the land border in terms of goods and thus speed up the border check processes in a secure and reliable manner. The ODYSSEUS platform will be applicable for both land and water scenarios including on the road, in a maritime port, and in the train.

ODYSSEUS has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N°101073910.

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Website goes live

odysseusproject.eu

The website of the **ODYSSEUS** project went live with many features providing all the information about our project, including our goals, objectives, partners, and latest updates.

[VISIT](#)

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ODYSSEUS Media Kit

Discover ODYSSEUS Promotional Materials!

A roll-up banner for the ODYSSEUS project. At the top is the ODYSSEUS logo and the title "Unobtrusive Technologies for Secure and Seamless Border Crossing for Travel Facilitation". Below this is a paragraph of text: "Seamless, Secure Border Crossing. Enhancing border checks, traveler experience, and law enforcement efficiency. Advanced identity verification, mobile passport, and cutting-edge screening technologies. Demonstrating effectiveness in real-life environments for rapid adoption by border management stakeholders." A QR code is in the bottom left of this section. The middle section is titled "Project Facts" and lists: Duration: 36 months, Start Date: 1st January 2023, Total cost: €4.59 million, and Project Coordinator: Ms Monica Florea, SIMAVI - Software Imagination & Vision. Below this is a "Technologies" section with icons for: Digital and Virtual Passport, Vehicle Scanning X-Ray Technologies, Faceless GDPR Compliant Travellers Counting, Seamless Identity Verification, AI-powered Behavioural Authentication, UAV-Assisted Vehicle Scanning, and Multi-Modal Fusion and DSS equipped X-AI. A "PILOTS" section shows a timeline for TRAIN, LAND, and WATER. The bottom section lists the Consortium members: SIMAVI, Rapiscan, AS-E, quadible, ACCELIGENCE, SQUAREITY, vision-box, Elenstar Technologies, THALES, ISIG, and YIC. At the very bottom is a small text block: "ODYSSEUS has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Innovation Programme under GA N°10107390. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency, neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them."

All relevant information about the brand is incorporated within the **ODDYSEUS media kit**.

You can download the leaflet, roll-up banner, and logo in high resolution from this page.

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ODYSSEUS Presentation

at the 18th UIC World Security Congress

The project was presented at the **18th UIC World Security Congress**, held in Jaipur, India from 21 to 23 February 2023.

The **18th edition of the UIC World Security Congress** brought together approximately 100 participants from 23 countries across the entire UIC network under the theme “Railway Security Strategy: Responses and Vision for the Future”

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ODYSSEUS presented

at the RISE-SD Conference 2023

The project coordinator, SIMAVI, delivered a comprehensive presentation on the **ODYSSEUS** project at the “Research and Innovation Symposium for European SECURITY and Defence” (RISE SD) event, held on the beautiful island of Rhodes, Greece, from May 29 to May 31, 2023..

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ODYSSEUS

1st Plenary Meeting

the journey continues

The **1st ODYSSEUS Plenary Meeting** was a resounding success! Held in Prague, Czech Republic, on June 26th and 27th, 2023, the consortium gathered for fruitful collaboration and progress.

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CONSORTIUM

STAY TUNED FOR UPCOMING ACTIVITIES, EVENTS, AND OPPORTUNITIES TO ENGAGE WITH THE PROJECT!